

Features of the legal regulation of a sports contract with woman professional athletes

Musaev Elbek Tayufovich

Acting professor of the Civil Law Department

of Tashkent State University of Law,

PhD in Law,

E-mail: elbek_m@list.ru

Annotation

The article touches upon the peculiarities of the terms of a sports contract concluded with a professional athlete, and analyzes the problems of legal regulation of such conditions. Attention is paid to the legal acts governing these relations, as well as the conditions on which the parties agree when concluding a professional contract for an athlete. It is noted that sports contracts have a complex legal nature. They interact with the norms of both civil and labor law. It is concluded that in a sports contract it is necessary to exclude some of the athlete's responsibilities related to the limitation of her personal rights.

Keywords: sport, law, sports relations, sports contract, contract terms, professional athlete, national legislation.

Physical culture and sport play an undeniable role in the life of any society, having a profound impact on health, social integration, personal development and the formation of universal human values. These areas are not just fun or physical strengthening activities, but have long-term positive consequences for everyone in society.

In our country, special importance is attached to the development of this area. Article 48 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "The state creates conditions for the development of physical culture and sports, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among the population." [1] In his speeches, the President of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, repeatedly focused on the importance of physical culture and sports for the state, society and the individual. [2] The country has adopted the Concept for the development of physical culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025. [3]

Studying and improving the norms of sports law at the present stage is becoming increasingly important.

One of the topics that, in our opinion, should be given more attention in the field of sports law is the legal aspects of contractual relations in sports. The activities of an athlete in our country, as well as activities in other areas, must comply with the principles established by regulations.

Today, in our opinion, the issues of legal regulation of a sports contract are very important. In this regard, it would be interesting to look at some of the problems with the terms contained in the sports contract with professional athletes.

The rights and obligations of athletes, including female athletes, and their social protection are regulated by the norms of national and international sports legislation.

The norms of the current national legislation regulating the professional activities of female athletes give reason to say that currently a professional athlete is, on the one hand, an ordinary employee, but on the other hand, an unusual subject of labor relations. Currently, the legislation on physical culture and sports establishes some features of the legal regulation of the work of professional athletes. They must be subject to the rules on employment contracts, working hours, rest periods, remuneration and labor protection, disciplinary and financial liability. However, labor legislation recognizes the specifics of such relationships. Therefore, regulation of the work of female athletes should be of a special nature. For example, categories such as “personal rights”, “transfer”, “rent of an athlete”, “working time of an athlete”, “image rights”, etc. should be taken into account.

The nature of sports activity determines the need to use those rules of law that can best ensure legal regulation of the work of professional female athletes.

The main regulatory documents in the field of development of physical culture and sports are the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Culture and Sports”, and labor sports activities are the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Article 25 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Culture and Sports” states that an athlete, like any athlete, has the right to “conclude employment contracts with physical culture, sports and other organizations in the manner prescribed by law.” [4]

“Based on practice, it can be stated that the activities of professional athletes are regulated by the labor legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as norms developed on the basis of the charters of international and national physical education and sports organizations and approved by professional physical education and sports associations in agreement with the republican federations for the relevant sports.” . [5]

The contract for sports activities is concluded on the basis of the labor legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and is an agreement in writing between the athlete and the head of the physical culture and sports organization.

The contract must contain the athlete’s responsibilities, her rights to social and health insurance, and the conditions for concluding and terminating the contract. A sports activity contract may contain other terms and obligations. A physical culture and sports organization provides the athlete with conditions for preparing for and participating in sports competitions, timely payment of wages, and fulfills other obligations stipulated by the contract on sports activities and not contradicting the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As follows from the above definitions, the terms of the contract for sports activities do not include any provisions that differ from the terms of the employment contract. However, a contract on sports activities must provide for special conditions for its conclusion and termination, unknown to the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, due to the characteristics of professional sports.

The work of professional athletes has its own characteristics and is regulated by legislation taking into account these characteristics, which is reflected in the relevant laws and other regulatory legal acts.

The issue we are studying is reflected in the legislation of many countries, where the legal regulation of sports relations is enshrined in laws and regulations. (Brazil, Argentina, Germany, France, Great Britain, Spain and many others.)

Thus, Brazilian Law No. 6354 of September 2, 1976 regulated “issues of concluding terms of agreement with professional athletes and sportswomen.” [6]

The specific responsibilities of female athletes include, for example, the obligation to compete only for a certain team, to play at full strength, to maintain their physical and psychological condition at the proper level, and to persistently and persistently improve their sportsmanship.

So, according to paragraph b of Art. 19 of the Argentine Law “Status of a Professional Football Player”, a professional athlete - a football player is obliged to maintain and improve his skills and psychosomatic functions for the implementation of sports activities, the decrease or loss of which through the fault of the player will be considered a serious breach of obligations. [7] Article 5 of the KHL (Continental Hockey League) Regulations establishes that a hockey player must constantly be in optimal sports shape throughout the entire hockey season. [8] The same requirements apply to female athletes.

The contracts of many professional football clubs in Uzbekistan also contain requirements for female athletes not to reduce a certain level of sportsmanship stipulated in the contract. [9]

Another non-standard responsibility is maintaining a sports regime. Thus, the legal definition of a sports regime is established by Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus “On Physical Culture and Sports”, which means the order of behavior of an athlete during sporting events and the athlete’s daily routine, including the regime of training and (or) competitive work, rest periods, nutrition, recovery, participation in medical examinations. [10] A similar definition is found in Australian law. [11] The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Culture and Sports” does not contain such a definition. However, it is logically clear that adherence to a sports regime is one of the employer’s requirements for a professional athlete. In addition, compliance with the sports regime is in the interests of the athlete herself, because achieving a high sports result, as a goal specified in the contract, is often impossible without following the regime. Therefore, many heads of sports clubs include these conditions in the contract with athletes.

Another specific feature of a sports contract is the provision limiting the personal rights of female athletes. The contract with athletes may include restrictions such as a ban on public performances, marriage and the birth of children during the period of the contract.

Unfortunately, these contract terms, previously unknown to national legislation, were often included in contracts with professional athletes, which clearly contradicts the norms of the Civil Code, as limiting the personal rights of the athlete. However, as noted above, such conditions were an objective necessity for achieving high results and were discussed in advance with the athlete and included in the contract with her consent. A reasonable question arises: is this legal?

Also, in some agreements there may be a provision that the athlete grants a sports organization, for example, a club for a certain sport, exclusive rights to use her image, i.e. exclusive right to use the name, image, photo and video images, graphic and any other images. As German researcher Juergen Schnabel notes, “contractual provisions for the transfer of image rights from players to their clubs and corresponding compensation provisions have received high priority.” [12] French law gives sports clubs and their athletes the opportunity to exclude the use of image rights from the employment contract and enter into a separate licensing agreement for image rights. [13] Royalty payments from unrelated marketing companies for the commercialization of individual image rights of female athletes are not subject to social security contributions and are not subject to any rules of sports federations in France. In the UK, these marketing companies are often owned by the sportsmen and women themselves. [14]

According to some authors, the provision in the contract with athletes regarding the transfer of exclusive rights to use their image contradicts the current legislation, because Some of the listed rights relate to inalienable personal non-property rights (the right to a name), and also require the consent of the athlete and appropriate remuneration to the athlete. [15] And in Germany, Articles 1 and 2 of the Constitution protect image rights. [16]

Let us add that in accordance with Article 42 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Culture and Sports”, “Relationships between institutions and organizations with minor athletes and sportswomen are carried out in the prescribed manner only with the consent and participation of their parents or persons in loco parentis, or specialized institutions, of which they are students,” [4] which is important when concluding a contract with minor athletes.

The practice of concluding contracts with professional athletes shows that legal norms are not only not followed, but are often violated. Contracts concluded with professional athletes include provisions that infringe on their labor and personal rights. The application of such provisions, as noted above, is explained by the special legal relations that arise in the field of professional sports, which is not taken into account by labor legislation, and is also not clearly reflected in the legislation on physical culture and sports.

It is important that a professional athlete has the right to appeal to the International Sports Legal Institutes in the event of a violation of her rights and interests as an athlete, and also has the right to their legal protection at the international level.

In the author's previous works it was pointed out that the sports contract should be considered mixed, because it contains conditions regulated by both civil and labor legislation. [17,18] Therefore, in our opinion, changes should be made not only to the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but also to national labor legislation.

Based on the foregoing, we propose to introduce into national legislation a rule prohibiting the inclusion in a contract with a professional athlete of conditions that limit her personal rights, namely, to supplement Article 503 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with paragraph 17 “on preventing the presence in the contract of a ban on marriage and birth children.” A similar norm should also be included in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Culture and Sports”.

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